

REINFORCING

News Release: EU-Funded Project REINFORCING Launches a Platform Pioneering a Central Hub for Open and Responsible Research & Innovation

13 November 2023 – The REINFORCING project kicked off in January 2023, bringing together 11 outstanding European partners. Funded by Horizon Europe, the EU's Framework Programme for Research, and Innovation (R&I), this initiative aims to contribute to a more inclusive R&I landscape by creating a hub for Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) practices.

REINFORCING efforts are directed at supporting European organizations, institutions, and territories in their transition towards a future where responsibility and openness are the driving forces behind research and innovation.

At the core of the project is the One-Stop Source platform designed to serve as the entry point to knowledge, training, and trainings on ORRI. The platform will select and curate the most interesting resources and centralize them in one single platform. Furthermore, the project provides unique networking opportunities for organizations, institutions and territories interested in becoming part of the European ecosystem that is transforming the R&I system by bringing it closer to society.

The project acknowledges that facilitating lasting change requires also financial support mechanisms to ensure the successful implementation of ORRI practices. Thus, REINFORCING has allocated funding for 96 cascading grants spread in 7 open calls, ranging from 20,000 to 60,000 euros. This financial support is specifically earmarked to help organizations and institutions scale up their ORRI expertise and provide support to new territories venturing into this field for the first time.

The first ORRI Open Call will support projects on Responsible Open Innovation, addressing specific challenges such as multi-stakeholder and Citizen Engagement, intellectual property rights mechanisms and impact assessment of responsibility. In addition, future calls will be focused on three key gaps already identified, Balkan territories and Mission projects.

The combined endeavors of these initiatives are anticipated to result in more than 150 sustainable institutional changes and the broad adoption of exemplary, transparent, and responsible Research and Innovation practices across the European Research Area.

You can learn more about the REINFORCING project at <https://reinforcing.eu/>

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